

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B107
Date: 04 Jul 2005
Take Off: 09:50:17
Landing: 14:37:09
Flight Time: 4h46m50

Campaign: ICEPIC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: SW

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottoway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jonathan Smith	Leeds University
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	CVI / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	CCN / AMS	Jonny Crozier	Manchester University
9	ADA/CPI	Paul Connolly	Manchester University
10			
11			
12			
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B107
 Date: 4th July, 2005
 Project: ICEPIC
 Location: Cornwall

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
084436		Start posn	0.51 kft	128	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
093825		INU	0.52 kft	128	Set to Navigate
095017		T/O	3.3 kft	290	Cranfield
095322		ASPs	5.0 kft	282	Open
095943		Videos	5.0 kft	268	FFC & RFC start
100337		EVM1	9.1 kft	246	Tail De-icing ON
102808	104207	Profile 1	18.0 - 4.3 kft	236	1000fpm
104334	104531	Run 1	4.7 kft	226	Icing, no good
104600	104749	Run 2	5.2 kft	226	Icing, no good
104924		Nevz	6.2 kft	208	Zero cal
105351	105648	Run 3	5.7 kft	131	Icing, no good
					New Cloud
110304	110428	Run 4	5.5 kft	103	1st lvl
110748	110907	Run 5	6.5 kft	283	2nd lvl
111309	111355	Run 6	7.1 kft	114	3rd lvl
111630	111819	Run 7	7.1 kft	296	4th lvl
					New Cloud
111910	112047	Run 8	7.0 kft	282	1st lvl
112405	112546	Run 9	7.7 kft	102	2nd lvl
112957	113056	Run 10	8.0 kft	260	3rd lvl
113422	113559	Run 11	9.0 kft	100	4th lvl
113936	114136	Run 12	9.7 kft	265	5th lvl
114459	114843	Run 13	10.4 - 10.3 kft	110	6th lvl
115214	115549	Run 14	10.8 kft	285	7th lvl
115935	120048	Run 15	11.0 kft	105	8th lvl
120422	120603	Run 16	11.2 kft	286	9th lvl
120956	121058	Run 17	11.5 kft	113	10th lvl
121425	121641	Run 18	11.8 kft	291	11th lvl
122939	123135	Profile 2	4.7 - 2.8 kft	026	1000fpm to 2.5k' on QNH 1006mB
123150	123543	Profile 2	2.7 - 0.50 kft	031	500fpm to 500' on QNH 1013mB
123557	124407	Run 19	0.51 - 0.60 kft	027	CCN sample failed
124914	130029	Run 20	0.49 - 0.51 kft	226	CCN sample failed
130318		Videos	5.0 kft	337	Change tapes
131308	132535	Run 21	2.5 kft	036	below cloud
133446	134639	Run 22	0.50 - 0.56 kft	238	CCN failed, Abort
133836		EVM2	0.46 kft	298	Turn reciprocal
134739	140016	Run 23	2.2 kft	057	CCN sample below cld
140729		ASPs	11.0 kft	057	Close
143709		Land	0.54 kft	348	Cranfield
144021		Stop posn	0.53 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B107 Track 04-JUL-05

PROJECT BRIEF: ICEPIC – development of ice and precipitation in cumulus clouds.

Scientific Aims: The goal of ICEPIC is to understand and quantify the formation and growth of ice particles in cumulus clouds. We wish to examine:

- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

As a first priority, in-situ aerosol and microphysical measurements from the aircraft will be gathered in close coordination with the CAMRa radar at Chilbolton, Hants. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C. The radar may identify columns of supercooled raindrops within the growing cumulus clouds that can be investigated more intensively by the aircraft.

Weather conditions: Developing showers that are forecast to have tops up to about -15°C within range of the Chilbolton radar. It may be preferable to fly to an alternative region away from the radar if conditions are more suitable.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. Information on current location of lightning (sferics) can be provided by FAAM using the NAMIS system. Several aircraft will be operating in the boundary layer at the same time as part of CSIP: UFAM Cessna - entire project; German DO-128 - 20 June to 17 July; NERC DO-228 - August. (The BAS Twin Otter may also participate in CSIP.)

Key instruments and their operation

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- FWVS
- GPS (including cruciform), INU, turbulence probe When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP (or CIP-100), PCASP, SID-1 (*and* SID-2). Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, pristine ice crystal habits, large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery above freezing level.
- (ADA)/CPI as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator (2min reqd.) whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest.
- *Ice Nucleus counter (INC) will normally be operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to different conditions.*
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. When straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- AMS - min 2mins (~12km) reqd for size-resolved composition distribution.
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode

- above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode to sample cloud particle residues into the AMS.

SORTIE BRIEF: ICEPIC ICE and Precipitation Initiation in Cumulus clouds

Flight Number: B107

Date: 4th July 2005

Mission Scientist: Jonathan Smith

Sortie Aims: To measure development of microphysics and dynamics in cumulus cloud systems.

Location: Amongst developing cumulus clouds within 1-5 hours transit of Cranfield. Area Alpha, with preference be to west of Chilbolton radar facility (to be within radar range).

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise inflow atmosphere around and below developing cumulus – *where not done by CSIP*
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds, preferably near the top of growing turrets, through the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be *with wings level*. Three principal options are for:
 - A well-defined isolated clouds
 - B many clouds (RICO scenario)
 - C organised convection on a convergence line or a gust front.

Meteorological information will be given from the CSIP Operations Centre at Chilbolton before flight and in-flight (using VHF radio, new frequency is 130.575 MHz, call-sign remains “Radsearch”).

Sortie Detail

1. Out-of-Cloud: only where not done by CSIP

- 1.1. Take off and climb for transit to the operating area. Locate suitable growing cumulus. 40+ min
- 1.2. *Optional profile descent in clear air, 1000 ft/min, FL200 to 500 ft agl. If necessary step profile to stay in area. (Not required at Chilbolton) Set altitudes and directions for later[†].* 25 min
- 1.3. Run at 500 ft agl, minimum length 50 km along suitable azimuth (across line or front for Option C) to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require initial delay to settle instruments. 10 min
- 1.4. Ascend to 500 ft below cloud base and carry out 50 km run on suitable azimuth to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require delay after ascent to settle instruments. 15 min

2. Cloud Work Options

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with clouds, near their top

- A.1. Proceed to about 0° C altitude[†], or below max cloud top if lower 5 min
- A.2. Adjust altitude to 500 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude. It is important to penetrate the growing turret, updraught, region. Once clear of cloud, continue run for 10 s then procedure turn to return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible. 5 min
- A.3. As time permits, repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) until T = -20° C[†].
{ Vertical separation of repeats set to match growth of cloud } 45 min

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample many clouds

- B.1. Proceed to 0° C altitude[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min
- B.2. Commence 10 min run in along shear direction[†]. Adjust track to randomly sample growing turret / updraught regions of cloud but without passing through RED radar echoes (reflectivities of 37 dBZ or greater). End run clear of cloud. 10 min
- B.3. As time permits, repeat an ascent by -3° C[†] (approximately 1500 ft) followed by a run as in B.2 until the lowest of -15° C[†] or max cloud top is reached. (-3, -6, -9, -12, -15° C[†]) 75 min

Option C: Clouds with linear organization (eg. along a convergence line or gust front).

- C.1. Proceed to 0° C[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min
- C.2. Fly leg perpendicular to line, length as required. Adjust track to penetrate cloud tops or cell centres. End run clear of cloud. 2 min
- C.3. As time permits, repeat a 180° turn and ascent followed by C.2. Ascent either; as A to 500 ft below cloud tops until -20° C[†] reached, or as B at fixed temperature levels. 30+ min

3. Repeat If time permits, for new developing cumulus carry out Option A, B or C.

Transit return at any suitable altitude. 40+ min

CWVC
+ ICE PIC
for tomorrow

Bob

Mission Scientist's Log 00441234 754 864
Jonathan Smith Alan Wadley 754 533

Flight No **B**.....107
FAAM © 2004

Date 4th July '05

Page 1 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
9:50	climb	2500			pass cloud base or climb out
9:51	"	4500			1/8 Cu ^{below} 3/8 Sc above
09:59	trist	5000	268°	52°N/15°W	just out of cloud now 3/8 Cu below 3/8 Sc above
10:01		6500			CPI sees ice crystals T = -1°C
10:04					tail icing on for last 2 minutes T = -4°C
10:05					8W LWC 0.01 / Now 0.21 gm ⁻³
10:06		14,900		51.8°N/23°W	deeper above 3/8 Ci 1/8 Sc 2/8 Cu T-17 just over land end of Gerem estuary on track p61
Bob 9:30Z	interesting feature at			50;13N / 5.50W	line ext SE from
10:25	trist	FL180			two pictures, one of screen after hands are given by Bob
	clouds look good here			51.2°N/11.2°W	some lines coming in to land
	PI ^{sketch}				2/8 Cu 3/8 As ahead - level with us
		12900		50.9°N 50°W	T-15
		10,500		50.8°N 51°W	- 9
		9000		50.7°N 52°W	- 6
10:37:59					turn to N to look at developing cloud
					- 3
		5000ft			0

deide
 CWK or
 10:50:12
 tomorrow

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.107**.....

Date 4th July '05.....

Page 2 of 7.....

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	ed P1				
	R2 now break out			at 4500 up to 5000 ft.	
				maybe a bit low on cloud	1'30s thru cloud
10:49:48					too late on that
10:52:20					new cloud near body End
10:55:19				maybe 800 ft	~ 30s across cloud
				ice again at end of run - Ci above	
11:00					could be reason
	look for new				
	start R4				picture new cloud T+0.5
				Falmouth	~ 25s thru cloud
				over Dart River	no ice seen by CPI
11:07				picture before run	height looks good
10:09:23					11s across
				height looked good	
				picture of Nanyung	
					4/8 Ci above - old and ?
					quite broken
	R6	bt high	tunnel B	left me what we had	
				11s through bit high	nothing on radar
				not growing so go to another	
	R8 next	cloud		FLO70	11:

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:26					30s thru main cloud at
		some thinner	cloud		ahead of main cloud
R9		FL077			v. thin Ci above
					20s over that 1st then
end R9					into another
	→	cloud ahead of main			part?? T now -4.27
		two kmets			11s or so thru 3rd
turn on after R10		a couple of			seconds thru next.
		FL090			now at limit set by AT T-5.5
11:35:54					out of second cloud as well
					now run at FL100
		CP1 sees			some ice in 2nd cloud
11:38:59		drop down a bit			- not quite at FL100
11:41:56		gap in middle of			1st cloud
		15s thru			second cloud looked to be same height
		into cloud			
		updraft in last 50m			- 8ms ⁻¹ to 17ms ⁻¹ ±4ms ⁻¹
11:47:00	run	continues to next cloud			+ another picture
		less echo on radar			
	→	gap in middle of this second cloud			
		no rain on cockpit roof either			
11:52:08	R14	FL108			into second cloud looks good height
		bit high angle			
11:54		to original "rain" cloud + ech			
11:55:30		rain on roof			as well

← P1 - water on 1st cloud in R14
 rimed crystals on second - T was ~ -8°C

after B14 now at 11,300 ft over St Mangon on km

pic ~~at~~ on 2nd one rain against T_{ic} -11

12:02 no second funnel now, just the "rain" one
go up 200 ft now, will it keep growing

picture echo

rain on cockpit 21s after a break
into second funnel " 40s to second funnel

12:06:36 go around

CP1 1st funnel very large ice, 2nd funnel only droplets

turn around to

12:10:30 rain on roof
canyon to next pod.

12:15:09

not so active now, decaying funnels left.

T -11°C

near top of cloud - its bright
long ~~line~~
+ also bumpy after the cloud

12:22 1/8 Ci (disturb to left) Cb to starboard 1 o'clock
more Cu over land 5/8 Cu

12:25 now on descent to resonance perfect
some large Cu ahead on this heady of 291

12:28 Prof. resonance looks to be under an old wind

but by 12:31 we past far edge $3/8$ Cu
Am just above cloud base huge to ~ 500 ft min
descent.

12:32:05 ~ a 2400 ft (2100 ft or instants?)

pass cloud base

925 hPa for cloud base

R19 - bit lumpy Cu to starboard + ahead, less to port.

$3/8$ Cu no Ci above $2/9$ Ci to starboard ahead

two pictures of sea state some swell, some white water
looks v. similar above, maybe more cloud to it,
some Cu to starboard ahead.

not enough time for CCN so will do on
second run at 500 ft a/c to Sealy Isles

12:52:58 232° hdg - wind is $9 \text{ m s}^{-1} / 293^\circ$ T +12.4°C
OR 6.6°C
50.8°N 5.4°W

12:56 picture, just a pretty cloud
and Am run + up to 500 ft CCN is not stabilizing
so is not met enough

Thosson
Sawtest
log

B107

Sheet 6 of 7

13:16:58 close to cloud base, but mistan
altitude for CCN Cb a little lower down here
50.8N 5.6W 2.5 kg

13:18 ~~is~~ cloud

13:21 - Cb now higher 51.0N 5.3W still in run
CCN in trouble

13:24:58 slight turn

end of Run 21 below cloud - RMS data but no
CCN

13:37:45 - CCN making now!

13:37:50 turn at 500 ft.

end Run 22 just 1 sample in CCN
now run below cloud base

started
low level runs at 12:35 → its taken an hour so far

30 miles passing hundy again ~ 500 ft below
cloud base

13:50:40 patch of contrails to starboard

approaching 'intensity' Cu over Welsh coast &
extending S.

CCN needs more time to complete samples
won't get it all

good set of numbers on
CCN at last!

clear of
Ci above
Cu 3/8

Wissam
Scientist
log

B107

Page 7 of 7

1h:06 quite a few Ct cloud here inland of ~~Bristol~~ ^{Cardiff}

looks a bit more active than the forecast

1h:09 clouds to N of Severn - on route to Brecon

CV1 - looks OK now

CCN - paper in buffer

1h:16 pass through rain, lots of rain ahead

1h:21 bit bumpy at edge of a cloud

end 14:35 or about

Debrief 16:15h

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Y
All cylinders pressures are OK	Y
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	Y

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	80	103	80
POST FLIGHT	70	102	80

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.3	0.35	1.112	0.067	U/S
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
Synced @ 08:32:40	30.32 adj. to 34.04	1.33 adj. To 1.60	6.46 adj. To 7.15	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-2	-1	-1	-1	0	0	
NO (ppbV)	0.11	0.3	-0.05	-0.10	-0.16	-0.22	-0.22
NO₂ (ppbV)	-0.51	-0.53	-0.50	-0.47	-0.43	-0.44	-0.48
NO_x (ppbV)	-0.40	-0.50	-0.55	-0.53	-0.59	-0.66	-0.54
SO₂ (ppbV)	U/S	U/S	U/S	U/S	U/S	U/S	-

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

N2 standard gas pressure dropped over the weekend from 57 bar to empty. May be bottle wasn't 100% (though I'm sure it was) closed but may be a leak in the seal between bottle and tap.

SO₂ lamp intensity far too low (3Hz – should be 16000Hz). Rebooting didn't help so switched off.

FLIGHT NUMBER: B107	DATE: 04 Jul 2005	OPERATOR: Pre flight: Doug Anderson Post flight: Doug Anderson	Page 2 of 2
PROJECT: ICEPIC			

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)

Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
09:07:33	Ground (pre flight) (1001!)	80.53	95.70	7707.16	47.86	7.06
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator
		33.27	-	-	-	-

Time	Flight Level	Remarks
09:09		CO valve switch gave value of 509-514 rather than 1001 as above so second cal done, see below

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
09:13:34	ground (508-514)	79.58	97.21	7735.98	48.20	6.88	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		32.74	0.30	0.35	1.112	0.067	U/S

Time	Flight Level	Remarks
In flight	-	Unmanned auto cals in flight.

Time	Flight Level	CO				
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
14:37:19	FL046 or FL050 (515-527)	79.27	97.47	7726.48		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)				
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

Nil

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B107

Date: 4 July 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

Page 1 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:55:00											PCASP heater ON
10:05:00											Transit Large drops to wet snow to snow as temp drop through 0 to -18 in cloud Profile 1
10:28:08											
10:29:00	24	0.1	189	0	0	0		0	0		F1170
10:30:00	17	0	189	0	0	0		0	0		F1160
10:31:00	39	0	189	0	0	0		0	0		F1150
10:32:00	35	0.09	189	0	0	0		0	0		F1140
10:33:00	38	0.09	189	0	0	0		0	0		F1130
10:34:00	38	0.09	189	0	0	0		0	0		F1120
10:35:00	25	0.09	189	0	0	0		0	0		F1110
10:36:00	24	0.07	189	0	0	0		0	0		F1100
10:37	41	0.08	189	0	0	0		0	0		F190
10:38	22	0.09	189	0	0	0		0	0		F180
10:39:20	16	0.07	189	5	0	0		0	0		F170
10:40:20	22	0.09	189	10	0	0		0	0		F160
10:4120	80	0.09	189	10	0	0		0	0		F150
10:42	55	0.09	189	10	0	0		0	0		F140
10:43:34	63	0.1	189	10	0	0		0	0		Run 1 fl47
10:46	300	0.11	194	1000	800		2	148	725	2	Run 2 fl52
10:53:51	23	0.08	215	10	0	0		0	0		Run 3 fl57
10:56	300	0.3	224	1000	250		1	1400			
11:03:04	33	0.08	231	10	0	0		0	0		Run 4 fl 55
	300	0.6	258	1000							

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B107

Date:4 July 05

Operator:Jim Crawford

Page2 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
	22	0.08	279	0	0	0		0	0		Run 5 fl 65
11:08:38	222	0.55	285	1000							
11:13:09											Run 6 fl71 clear of cloud
11:13:45											In cloud
11:16:30											Run 7 fl 71 clear
11:17:45											In cloud
11:18:00			296								
11:19:10											Run 8 fl 70 clear
11:20:20											In cloud
11:24:05											Run 9 fl77 clear
11:25:13											In cloud
11:29:57											Run 10 fl 80 clear
11:30:25			382	3000							In Cloud
11:34:22											Run 11 fl 90 clear
11:34:40											In cloud
11:35:40											In cloud
11:39:36											Run 12 fl 97 clear
11:40:08											In cloud
11:41:10											In cloud

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B107

Date: 4 July 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

Page 3 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:45:00											Rum 13 fl 103 clear
11:46:00											In cloud
11:48:20											In cloud
11:52:14											Rum 14 fl 108 clear
11:53:16											In cloud
11:55:30											In cloud
11:59:35											Rum 15 fl 110 clear
12:00:17											In cloud
12:04:22											Rum 16 fl 111 clear
12:05:10	300	0.49	501	5000							In cloud
12:09:56											Rum 17 fl 115 clear
12:10:15											In cloud
12:14:25											Rum 18 fl 118 clear
12:15:44											In cloud
12:29:39											Profile 2 clear 2600ft descent rate 500 f/m
12:35:52											End of profile 2

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B107

Date: 4 July 2005

Operator: Jim Crawford

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:35:43	48	0.1	620	10	0	0		0	0		Run 19 500ft
12:38:00	64	0.1	620	20	0	0		0	0		
12:40:00	90	0.1	620	30	0	0		0	0		
12:42:00	100	0.09	620	30	0	0		0	0		
12:44:00	70	0.1	620	30	0	0		0	0		
12:49:14	73	0.08	620	20	0	0		0	0		Run 20 500ft
12:51:00	100	0.11	620	20	0	0		0	0		
12:53:00	130	0.07	620	20	0	0		0	0		
12:55:00	74	0.1	620	20	0	0		0	0		
12:59:00	100	0.07	620	20	0	0		0	0		
13:13:08											Run 21 2500ft
13:14:00	54	0.11	622	30	0	0		0	0		
13:16:00	52	0.12	622	100	0	0		0	0		
13:18:00	48	0.11	623	1000	0	0		0	0		
13:20:00	51	0.08	629	100	0.5	0		0	0		
13:22:00	40	0.1	630	100	0	0		0	0		
13:24:00	45	0.13	630	30	0	0		0	0		
13:22:32											End
13:34:46											Run 22 500ft
13:36:00	57	0.1	654	20	0	0		0	0		
13:38:00	53	0.08	654	20	0	0		0	0		
13:40:00	38	0.08	654	20	0	0		0	0		
13:44:00	100	0.07	654	30	0	0		0	0		
13:46:00	100	0.07	654	20	0	0		0	0		

CLoud PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B107

Date: 04/07/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	Y Y	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	Y	CONDOR
3) Log on to FLOODS run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_output_binary a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA:	Y Y	Complete, no errors. *.txt files deleted after
4) run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_extract_tas a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	Y 0 240000	Completed
5) run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_read a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]	Y Y 0 Y	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL21062005.txt Completed
6) In PVWAVE a) .run mrfb:[pms.proc]ffssp_sec_read .run mrfb:[pms.proc]lag b) .run mrfb:[pms.proc]write_procffssp_to_m5 c) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format d) exit	Y Y	Correceted for lag of -16 secs with JW data Completed
7) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name	Y	Completed (left as mfd)

			set at 0
e) TAS:	Y	Y	
f) MFD directory:	MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX		
g) Probe number:	(1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty	0	
h) Start time:	0 if unkown	0	
i) End time:	240000 if unknown	240000	
j) Nominal averaging:	0.2 seconds for conversion to M5	0.2	
k) Particle type:	8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown	8	
l) Coefficient choice:	2	2	
m) Output root filename:	PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	Y	Completed
10) In PVWAVE			
i) .run MRFB:[PMS.PROC]WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5			
ii) write_proc2d_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_proc2d.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2d'			
iii) exit			Completed
11) MODIFY			
a) Modifying datasets:	pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D		
b) Datset:	mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX		
c) New dataset:	Enter modified MFD name		Completed (left as mfda)

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B107

Date: 04/07/2005

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm3/sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: 0 if unknown h) End time: 240000 if unknown	1 0.7 0 0 240000	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate B104 = 0.8, B110 = 0.6 Do not have cloud physics log for B109 so set at 0.7 Not in cloud physics log so set at 0 Completed
3) In PVWAVE i) .run MRFB:[PMS.PROC]WRITE_PROCPCASP_TO_M5 ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' iii) exit		
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name	Y	Completed. MFD renamed as B107_mfdb

Flight No B107

CCNC LOG

J Croster, Unit of Man

Exp. ICE PIC

Date 4/7/2005

Page 1 of

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	D ₁ D ₂	STATIC						REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5		
1236:70	1236:30	500ft	20-85	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		} puller up!!
				0.40					S	
				439					D	
				527					B	
				2382					R	
				1001					P	
1264:13	1264:50	500ft	25-65	0.60					S	} paper on top of bell.
				474					D	
				2370					B	
				1001.4					R	
									P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
1313:16	1313:50	2-50	24-59	0.50					S	} not stabilized
				1201					D	
				2315					B	
				1001.5					R	
									P	
13:35:40	13:36:20	500ft	23-15	0.50					S	
				1209					D	
				1272					B	
				2213					R	
				1001.6					P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
1349			25-8	0.49	0.7	1.07	1.04	2.01	S	
			24-45	1225	1144	1334	1544	1810	D	
				1223	1143	1092	1047	1057	B	
				2255	2261	2278	2288	2297	R	
				1001	1001	1001	1001	1001	P	
									S	
									D	
									B	
									R	
									P	

@ 2000ft

2425 Tune

	old	New
Det in	4	18
Ref out	1	11
HB	-6.63	-6.63
Focus	15	15
Extr	238	236

EM cal

UV = 2.475
Gain = 3.63e6

-> Mass range cal

IE cal

IE = 2.167e6
ABms = 2.45e6
ABrof = 2.17e6
IC dD = 1.4e-6
Run SSD

IPProcs = 503
IPCHW = 568
RIG MW = 5.88e6

Postflight only

EM cal

W = 2.475

Gun = 281e6

IC cal

IE = 2.332e-6

ABms = 3.03 min.

ABsec = 2.63 min.

IC cal = 2.167e-6

Run 630 = GenAlt

631 = MS/TOF

IPPms = 542.05

IPPmin = 608.53

RTEmin = 3.867

FLIGHT B007
TCEPIC Flight

4/7/05
Monday

Fitted new mouse. Didn't realize there is a connection before the KVM. It was a real pain.

CPI fine - couldn't find rod for cleaning but windows OK.

ADA - laser power completely dead on both lasers, looked @ coupler alignment with crosshairs - completely out.

Looked @ crosshairs on fibre line - way out.

Noticed that shield from laser to fibre line is loose.

I think ADA needs a full alignment. Ran out of time.

Maybe try after flight.

After take off PDS levels went high. 20 → 8.9 intermittent
45 → 5.2

In transit @ -8°C, CPI is seeing mixed phase cloud - columns etc.

- Phone call - interesting line ^{feature.} in South Irish sea

$$\frac{1000000}{1000} \times 10^{-4} = 1000$$
$$\frac{0.5}{0.1} = 5$$
$$\frac{0.5}{100} \times 10^{-3} = 5 \times 10^{-3}$$

$$\frac{1000}{10} = 100$$
$$\frac{0.5}{10} = 5 \times 10^{-2} = 5 \text{ cm}$$

Start profile | 10:28:00

- CPI not seeing anything

- FL Manger

Mission Sci said to flying under a layer of stratus cloud & tell him if we see ice from above.

End @ 4000ft 104207

Start run 1 FL 47 104344
cloud penetration

Abort 104531

change to new level, 500ft ↑

Start run 2 | FL 52 104600

Droplet - ice!

big drops

End 2 104749

2nd penetration

Start on 3 FL 57 105351

- Droplets
 - Big drops - 100µm
 - ice @ cloud edges.
- 2DC says wet snow?

End 105648 T = -1°C

Over land 3rd penetration

Start on 4 FL 55 110304

- Droplet
 - gap
 - droplet
- } no ice.

End on 4 110428

Again need coast line
4th penetration

Start on 5 FL 65 110748

- Note from Cpt. we are near
danger area.

- & lets
 - Big drops
- } no ice

End on 5 110907

Over land. 5th penetration.

Start on 6 FL 71 111309

droplets small

End on 6 111355

turret → 6th penetration
(Stopped growing?)

Start on 7 FL 71 111630

droplet a little larger

End of on 7 111819

Another cloud! new coastline

Start # FL 70 m 8 111910

Bigger droplets
* ice in low # one
Mostly droplets

End m 8 112047

2nd penetration

Start m 9 FL 77 112405

drops quite large - intermediate

End m 9 112506

3rd penetration

Start m 10 FL 80 112957

droplets

* 2 turrets

End m 10 113056

4th penetration?

Start m 11 FL 90 113422

drops big
turbulent!

Saw ice!
mostly droplets

End m 11 @ 113559

1st pass

Start m 12 FL 97 113936

drops high # one
Cpt. original cloud next? straight ahead

drops lots
a couple ice inges

End 114136

sp 4 m/s⁻¹ updraughts

Start on 13 FL 103 114459

droplets
big bandcraft!
— clear AIR —

top in

droplets, big down draft!

T = ~ -8.5°C

End on 13 FA 114843

Looks like it glaciated

(Miss Sci)

Start 14 FL 108 115214

droplet in 1st no ice!

— clear air —
2nd turret

droplet — some ice
— mixed ice crystals

End 14 115542.

Start 15 FL ~~110~~ 115935

1st

ice & droplets — slightly
more than before
-9.8°C

End 15 120048

Start 16 FL 117 120422

heating Carbide turret

~ -10°C

Very large ice
& some droplets

— clear —
droplets only

End 120603

NB/ Miss. Sci — a lot going on
in turrets — they appear different
even though there are similar heights

Start 17 FL 113 12 09₅₆

mixed plate
droplets
capric columns
mixed droplets

End 17 12 10 58

Start 18 FL 118 12 14 25

ice nearly all
some v. large ice
possibly some droplets?

End 18 12 16 41

Start profile 2 FL 117 12 29 39
↙ 05

End 12 35 43

below cloud base over 0 cum.

Start run 19 FL 051 12 35 57

end run 19 12 44 07
- problem with CCN - not enough time
drop down redo...

Start run 20 FL 050 12 49 14

End 20 13 00 29
still problem with CCN

Start run 21 FL 25 13 13 08

below cloud base run

Problems with CCN

End 21 13 25 35

Run 22 50qt 13 34 46

End 22 13 46 39

Run 23 @ 2000 13:4739

End 23 140016

Updrafts, pinhins, temperature
altitude, map.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B107**

Date: 04/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	N	
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B107

Date: 04/07/05

Instruments

1. Video – DFC display out of focus. Inboard display always in standby mode.
2. RFC / DFC – Text on camera displays changed to match camera position.

Rack instrument status

ADA - not working

CPI, Cloud Physics & AMS – all fine

CVI – appears to have been overfilled with butanol recently, now okay

CCN - top paper fell into chamber during 1st sample run. Replaced. Then some stray bytes got into buffer and caused sample analysis problems. Now okay, got good spectrum before return transit.

Aircraft

1. Problem with pre-ignition on No. 2 engine

Satcom H:- 1 call made by Leeds University

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B107:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Jonathan Smith
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

8mm video recordings from this flight reside with :

Professor Alan Blyth

The School of the Environment
University of Leeds
Leeds
LS2 9JT
UK

Tel: +44 (0)113 3436461
Fax: +44 (0)113 3436716

E-mail: blyth@env.leeds.ac.uk

0930Z

Seattle looks at
50°20' N 6°W
now at 0930Z
from Bob at 50°13' N 5°50' W
-think its minor-